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Evaluating of Salinity Tolerance and Aroma of Rice Lines at BC3F5 Generation In The Mekong Delta, Vietnam

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Abstract

Rice (*Oryza sativa*) is one of the most important food crop in Vietnam, so it is imperative to select rice varieties with high quality and adaptive to climate change. This study assessed the salinity tolerance and aromatic characteristics of 5 rice lines of the the BC3F5 generation through agronomic characteristics and molecular biology techniques. Results showed that all rice lines grew at 4 ‰ salt concentration and outperformed compared to control line and was assessed to be aromatic. The P36 rice line was evaluated for carrying the gene for salinity resistance through marker RM206 with amplicon size of 147 bp, similar to Pokkali, a standard line for salt resistance. Due to genotypic analysis, this line was also indicated as recessive homozygous for frg gene, which controls aromatic trait. Based on the higher yield and other agronomic parameters compared to Jasmine 85 and FL478 varieties, P36 line was considered as a promising materials for breeding programs.

Keywords: Salinity Tolerance, Aroma of Rice, BC3F5 Generation

INTRODUCTION

Rice (*Oryza* spp.) is an important crop which contributes 50-80% calories daily for human, especially low income people; moreover, rice is the main food for approximately 3 billion people around the world. Asia is responsible for 92% global rice yield and 90% of rice production is originated from small farms, so there is the dependence of their life on the rice price and crop security (Bandumula, 2017).

The salinity is a serious problem in rice cultivation which mainly happened in coastal area as the result of sea water invasion into the rice field (Mensvoort *et al.*, 1984; Gregorio *et al.*, 2002; Ismail *et al.*, 2010). About 48 million ha of potential agricultural soil in South and South East Asia became impossible for cultivation due to salinity. Salinity intrusion affected 1.7 million ha out of 3.9 million ha of land in Mekong delta (Wassmann *et al.*, 2004; Vo, 2012), resulting to extensive economic decrease. Previous studies illustrated that the salt tolerance is fluctuated during living stages, this trait is dominant during germination, becomes very sensitive throughout early seedling stage; however, tolerance is appeared at vegetative stage, again becomes sensitive at reproduction stage and then becomes dramatically more tolerant at maturity (Lutts *et al.*, 1995). The reliable and effective solution to address the problem of salinity is breeding and selection of a salt tolerant variety (Quijano-Guerta and Kirk, 2002). Thus, the important activity is to screen the local germplasms of paddy to identify the potential materials for breeding programs.

Aromatic rice is traded with high price in both local and international market due to excellent aroma and grain quality (Wakte *et al.*, 2017). In term of genetic, an expression of spontaneous recessive mutations of the OsBadh2 gene (also known as frg / badh2 / osbadh2 / os2AP gene) lead to aromatic phenotype. These mutations prevent the flow of \hat{U} -aminobutyraldehyde (GAB-ald) to \hat{U} -aminobutyric acid (GABA), and consequently, the accumulation of GAB-ald is converted to a potent flavor component 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline (2AP) (Prodhan and Qingyao, 2020). The utilization of DNA based molecular marker in plant breeding is more dominant compared to morphological method due the stability and less influence by environmental factors. Among the molecular marker technologies, microsatellite markers or SSR have been considered to

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be effective in identification of genetic variability among rice cultivars (Bhuiyan, 2005). SSR markers were codominant and highly polymorphic; offer an easy, accurate, and quantifiable measure of the genetic variation within crop plants (Sunnucks, 2000; Collard, 2008)

Therefore, the screening and selection of rice varieties for salt tolerance and aromatic trait plays a vital role for breeding projects. The aim of this study is to evaluate the level of salt tolerance and aroma from the BC₃F₅ generation of paddy rice in Mekong delta.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant materials

Five rice lines from the BC₃F₅ generation of Jasmine 85, the aromatic rice and Pokkali, the salt tolerant rice variety.

Screening of salinity tolerance

The phenotype of tolerant rice lines was evaluated based on screening method in artificial condition. Young plants were grown in Yoshida solution with 4‰ of NaCl (EC = 8 dS/m) following the modified procedure from IRRI (2002).

Sensory assay for aromatic trait

The presence of aroma was detected according to the method described by Sood and Siddiq (1978). Two grams of green leaves were collected from individual plants and cut into small pieces and kept in the test tubes. Ten mL of 1.7% potassium hydroxide (KOH) solution was poured to each test tube. The tubes were covered immediately and incubated at 65°C temperature for 20 minutes. These test tubes were opened one by one and was immediately evaluated by smelling. Parents are used as controls. The samples were scored on 0-2 scale with 0, 1 and 2 corresponding to non-aroma, slight aroma and aroma, respectively. Based on the mean of rating scale value, such rice lines were classified into 3 groups: aromatic (> 1.0), questionable (0.5-1.0), non - aromatic (< 0.5).

Evaluation of agronomic traits

Characteristics related to agronomy such as yield, plant height were analyzed according to method from Gregorio *et al.* (2002). Data is analyzed by using Minitab software version 16 for one way ANOVA with Duncan test.

Utilization of molecular marker for screening of aromatic and salt tolerant varieties

Genomic DNA was extracted from plant leaves after 15 growing days (~100 mg each) using CTAB method (Roger and Bendich, 1988). Aroma gene was detected by using BADH2 primer (Bradbury *et al.*, 2005) including EAP (5'-AGTGCTTTACAAAGTCCCGC-3'), ESP (5'-TTGTTTGGAGCTTGCTGATG-3'), INSP (5'-TGGTAAAAGATTATGGCTTCA-3') and IFAP (5'-CATAGGAGCAGCTGAAATATATACC-3') in a multiplex PCR. The reaction was carried out with the volume 25 µL containing 12 µL deionized water, 10 µL master mix 2X, 0.5 µL for each forward and reverse primer (the final concentration is 0.4 µM) and 2 µL DNA template. Thermal cycle was performed with initial denaturation at 95°C for 3 minutes followed by 35 cycles of 95°C for 30 second, 59°C for 30 second, 72°C 30 second and final extension at 72°C for 5 min before cooling at 10°C. Five SSR primer pairs (Table 1) were employed to select salt tolerance among such rice lines. PCR products were analyzed by 1.5% agarose electrophoresis and visualized under UV light by Gel documentation system (Bio-rad, USA).

Table 1: Sequences of SSR primers for detection of salt tolerance in rice

Primers	Nucleotide sequences	Motif	Annealing temperature (°C)	Product size (bp)
RM206	F-5'CCCATGCGTTTAACTATTCT3' R-5'CGTTCCATCGATCCGTATGG3'	(CT) ₂₁	55	147
RM225	F-5'TGCCCATATGGTCTGGATG3' R-5'GAAAGTGGATCAGGAAGGC3'	(CT) ₁₈	55	140
RM223	F-5'GAGTGAGCTTGGGCTGAAAC3' R-5'GAAGGCAAGTCTTGGCACTG	(CT) ₂₅	55	165
RM201	F-5'CTCGTTTATTACCTACAGTACC3' R-5'CTACCTCCTTTCTAGACCGATA3'	(CT) ₁₇	55	158
RM535	F-5'ACTACATACACGGCCCTTGC3' R-5'CTACGTGGACACCGTCACAC3'	(AG) ₁₁	55	138

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Evaluation of phenotype and genotype for salinity tolerance

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From the potential materials of BC₃F₅ generation, such rice lines were evaluated for the salt tolerance by cultivation in Yoshida solution with NaCl. The result showed that 6 rice lines were classified at the same salinity level with Pokkali and FL448 line. They were P35, P36, P37, P38, P39 and P40.

Genotype assessment for salinity and aroma

Marker RM206

The amplification was successful at all samples and the amplicon size was fluctuated from 150 to 200 bp. The gel pattern indicated that there were variations between different and even within rice line candidates (Fig. 1). There were polymorphic bands among individuals of P35 line when three samples expressed the band of 147 bp, similar to Pokkali and DP line, these lines were positive standards for salt tolerant rice. However, three other samples in P35 had the longer band, which belong to the susceptible line IR208. Thus, the purity of P35 line was not stable to use for commercial production. In addition, the band pattern was also different among samples of P37 and P38 lines. Two potential lines which showed the band of resistant standard were P36 and P39. The identical band of all samples reflected the purity of such two lines. RM206 marker has been confirmed for strong correlation with salt tolerance for rice varieties. Rana *et al.* (2009) identified the SSR marker for salt tolerance in F3 population of rice variety CSR10 and concluded that RM206 was significant association with Na/Ka ration phenotype. Moreover, this marker was also a useful indicator for bacterial blight resistance based on 1.9 cM near to Xa23 locus (Yusoff *et al.*, 2020).

Fig. 1: Gel pattern for amplification of RM206 primer
M-100 bp DNA ladder; Pok-Pokkali rice; DP-Doc Phung

The difference in band size between susceptible and resistant lines was not observed in case of four primers RM225, RM223, RM201 and RM535. RM225 (Fig.2-5) were indicated that marker RM225 linked to BPH resistance gene (*bph4*) (Chi *et al.*, 2019)

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Fig. 2: Gel pattern for amplification of RM225 primer
M-100 bp DNA ladder; Pok-Pokkali rice; DP-Doc Phung

Fig. 3: Gel pattern for amplification of RM223 primer
M-100 bp DNA ladder; Pok-Pokkali rice; DP-Doc Phung

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Fig. 4: Gel pattern for amplification of RM201 primer
M-100 bp DNA ladder; Pok-Pokkali rice; DP-Doc Phung

Fig. 5: Gel pattern for amplification of RM535 primer
M-100 bp DNA ladder; Pok-Pokkali rice; DP-Doc Phung

Aromatic traits

The aroma in rice is regulated by recessive homozygous stage of the *frg/frg* gene on chromosome 8. Presence of the enzyme BADH2 will decrease the content of substance 2AP, one of the main compound in aromatic rice. Meanwhile, the elimination of pairs nucleotides of this gene make SNPs which are enzyme BADH2 is inactivated so it accumulated compound 2AP sufficient threshold to create aroma of rice (Louis *et al.*, 2005). Four specific primers will give 2 bands size of 577 bp and 257 bp for recessive homozygous, 3 bands at size 577 bp, 355 bp and 257 bp for heterozygous, 2 bands in size size 577 bp and 355 bp for dominant homozygous. The results of aromatic gene tests on BC3F5 generation (Fig. 6) showed that PCR products with two bands of 577 bp and 257 bp for all rice varieties. Thus, it is possible to conclude that all hybrids carry two alleles of the recessive gene aroma in rice.

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Fig. 6: Gel pattern for aromatic gene detection in rice
M-100 bp DNA ladder; Pok-Pokkali; FL478

The hybrids were evaluated as aromatic rice (Table 2), four lines from P35 to P38 corresponding to the parent variety Jasmine 85, a standard aromatic and were noted as more aromatic than the other lines.

Table 2: Classification of aromatic level for rice line candidates based on KOH assay

Lines	P35	P36	P37	P38	P39	P40	FL478	Jasmine 85
Aromatic level	2	2	2	2	1	1	NA	2

Agronomic characteristics of rice lines in salt condition

The results of the evaluation of agronomic characteristics (Table 3) indicated that the two lines P36 and P37 had superior yield compared to the remaining rice lines and the aromatic line Jasmine 85. Furthermore, the lines P36 and P37 expressed the yield respectively. 715 and 750 g/m². In term of plant height, these rice lines are classified as medium height (97-125 cm), the P36 strain is significantly lower than the FL478 and Jasmine 85, offering an advantage in reducing the probability of falling but still ensure productivity. For other parameters such as branch length, Atena *et al.* (2016) showed that cotton length correlated with yield, varieties with large cotton length were more likely to carry seeds, this data showed that the two lines P36 and P37 had the similar length as the control line.

Table 3: Agronomic traits of rice lines in this study

Rice lines	Yields (g/m ²)	Height	Branch length	Number of branch	Number of Seeds	Number of poor quality seed	Weight (1000 seeds)	Theory yield (ton/ha)
P35	683,33c	105,70cd	22,87c	8,29bc	136,67b	19,93a	31,07ab	6,83c
P36	715,00a	107,47bcd	23,46bc	9,53ab	145,47b	15,27a	19,67ab	7,15b
P37	750,00a	112,27abc	23,53bc	7,27bc	162,40ab	15,00a	22,93a	7,50a
P38	688,33bc	103,12d	26,17a	6,47c	164,07ab	16,87a	21,40ab	6,88bc
P39	648,33d	114,00ab	26,50a	9,00abc	176,27a	17,40a	22,07a	6,48d

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P40	641,67d	116,20a	25,30ab	11,13a	138,33b	15,40a	18,43b	6,42d
FL478	641,67d	116,20a	25,30ab	11,13a	138,33b	15,40a	18,43b	6,42d
Jasmine 85	641,67d	116,20a	25,30ab	11,13a	138,33b	15,40a	18,43b	6,42d
P-value	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,001	0,514	0,001	0,00
CV%	1,61	2,24	3,30	10,07	6,62	18,61	5,72	1,61

Data in the column which has the same character is not different at significant level $\alpha = 0.05$

CONCLUSION

The test results showed that all clones grow well in Yoshida medium with 4% salt. P36 and P37 lines are more productive than parents. Sensory aroma assessment revealed aroma were observed in all hybrids, the lines P36 and P37 are noted to be more aromatic than the other lines. Genotypic evaluation results have been confirmed all hybrids carried aromatic genes. The P36 and P39 lines carry the salt resistance gene through amplification of the RM206 primer. Therefore, P36 line is a promising candidate for both salt tolerance and aroma, so this line should be invested by further studies in green house and field conditions.

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